

Analysis of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* in the Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*

Dr. Mohan Kumar Pokhrel ✉

Department of English, Tribhuvan University,
Mahendra Multiple Campus, Dharan, Nepal

Dr. Ram Prasad Rai

Assistant Professor of English, Ratna Rajyalaxmi Campus,
Tribhuvan University, Nepal

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Abstract:

The prime concern of this article is to unfold Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* who keeps on thinking the problems of others as his own problems through the Paurāṇic text. Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* unfurls in the pastoral setting of Vṛndāvana, where he delights in playful activities with the cowherd boys and shows miraculous activities. His playful activities unveils thoughtful philosophical truths, explicating the concept of dharma (righteousness), the law of karma (action), and the path of bhakti (devotion) as the means to attain moksha

(salvation) and transcendental bliss. The major objectives of this study are to explore the *līlās* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa; to explicate the ways of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās*, and to evaluate Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās* in the Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. To reveal Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* in the Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*, the researcher uses *līlā* theory of Śrīla Sanātana Gosvāmī. The theorist claims that playful activities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa are his *līlās*. The study is significant to analyze Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās* which are related for the wellbeing of others. The findings of this investigation endow with evidences that the text has used Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* to motivate readers to dedicate themselves to solve the problems of others as Śrī Kṛṣṇa does in the Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. The conclusion drawn from this investigation is Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās* are not merely stories but hold deep spiritual significance, teaching devotees about love, devotion, and the ultimate union with the divine.

Keywords: *Bāla līlā, bhakti yoga, rāsa līlā, miraculous activities, righteousness.*

Introduction

The Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* refers divine play or pastimes of Śrī Kṛṣṇa, who is considered the Supreme Personality of Godhead by the followers of Vaiṣṇavism. One finds the discussions of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* in the text from Śūkadeva Gosvāmī, the narrator and other characters like Sage Sūta, Brahmā, Uddhava, Sage Maitreya, and Prahlāda. They highlight the concept of *līlā* in the Śrīmad

Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa. On this ground, Śūkadeva is apt to state: "Let me offer my respectful obeisance onto the Supreme Personality of Godhead who, for the creation of the material world, accepts the three modes of nature" [*namaḥ parasmai puruṣāya bhūyase/ sad-udbhava-sthāna-nirodha-līlayā*] (*Bhāgavata* 2.4:12). The narrator regards creation of the cosmos of the divine being as his *līlā*. With the similar belief, C. L. Goswami notes that the supreme person performs "His

sportful activity of creating, preserving and destroying the universe" (100). To strengthen the argument, one can argue that the universe is created and will be destroyed according to the course of time. The *līlā* of the divine being motivates humans to perform their activities as *līlās* for a short-time. With this conditioning, G. V. Tagare (2007) supports that the perfect man uses his infinite power for creation, maintenance, and destruction of the universe (p.443). It shows that the concept of *līlā* begins from the analysis of the playful activities of the divine being.

In this context, it is instructive to mention the argument of Sage Sūta on *līlā*. In his words: "Assuming the roles of incarnations, He performs pastimes to reclaim those in the mode of pure goodness" [*līlāvatārānuratodevatiryāṅ-narādiṣu*] (1. 2: 34). It indicates that God incarnates in the universe for the performance of his *līlā*. But the *līlās* of the divine being is for well-being of all creatures. It is interesting to unveil the view of Prabhupāda (2012) to highlight *līlā* of God. In his corroboration: "He appears to be differently manifested according to the particular time" (p.140). The interpreter points out *līlā* the activities of the divine being. Explaining this statement, Bibek Debroy (2019) in his text *The Bhāgavata Purāṇa*, discusses that playful activities of God in creation, maintenance, and destruction of the world are His *līlās* (p. 29). The views of Śūkadeva and Sage Sūta are same on the definition of *līlā*. Those sages link the value of *līlā* in the activities of the divine beings.

Divine sages of the *Bhāgavata* highlight the *līlās* God in the universe. They seem to neglect *līlās* of human beings. Like Śūkadeva and Sage Sūta, Brahmā proves the importance of God's *līlā* from his argument: "Through the material qualities, You very easily create the universe, maintain it and again annihilate it" [*viśvasya sarga-sthiti-saṁyamān guṇaiḥ/ sva-līlayā sandadhate 'vyayātmane*] (7. 8:40). Brahmā reaches to the level of thinking *līlā* from the level of creation and destruction of the universe. To support this idea of *līlā*,

Pushpendra Kumar (2009: 606) remarks that the divine being "himself remains undecayed and unchanged'. It shows that the creation of the creator is destroyed according to the course of time but he remains same. To strengthen the argument, John Stratton Hawley (1981) in *At Play with Krishna* argues "Godhead into human form" (p. 59) for completion of his *līlā*. The discussion above shows that the creation of the universe is the outcome of divine being's *līlā*.

Uddhava has contradictory idea on *līlā* from Śūkadeva, Sūta and Brahmā in the *Bhāgavata*. He incorporates Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* as the basis of *līlā*. In his words:

The great wizards who were able to assume any form were engaged by the king of Bhoja, Kaṁsa, to kill Kṛṣṇa, but in the course of His pastimes the Lord killed them as easily as a child breaks dolls¹. (3.2:30)

To support the idea of *līlā*, Uddhava refers Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* in the text. It proves that Śrī Kṛṣṇa defeats all demons that are sent by Kaṁsa in the forms of animals and humans. Those demons are Aghāsura, Bakāsura, Sakatāsura, Dhenukāśura, and Putanā. It proves that Śrī Kṛṣṇa shows his *līlās* from the time of his childhood. With this idea at the centre of attention, G.V. Tagare (2007) claims that Śrī Kṛṣṇa "killed those wiley conjuring demons who could assume any form at will and who were deputed by Kaṁsa"(p. 230). With this logical description, we can argue that child Kṛṣṇa does not need too much effort to kill demons. Thus, Uddhava highlights heroic activities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa as his *līlās* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*.

Unlike the narrator and other characters of the text, Sage Maitreya examines Viṣṇu *līlā* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. The sage inspects: "In this manner the Personality of Godhead, Lord Viṣṇu, the maintainer of all living entities, raised the earth from within the water, and having placed it afloat on the water, He returned to His own abode" [*sa ittham bhagavān urvīm viṣvaksenaḥ prajāpatiḥ/rasāyālīlayannītām apsu nyasya*

yayau hatih] (3. 13: 47). Other above characters mention the *līlās* of divine being except Uddhava. But Sage Maitreya highlights Viṣṇu *līlā* from his argument. He believes that God Viṣṇu descends in the universe and returns to Vaikuntha after the completion of His *līlā*. From this standpoint, Ramesh Menon (2016) notes that God Viṣṇu comes to the world for his *līlā* (p.130). Explaining this statement, one can argue that *līlās* are the activities of divine beings in the universe. But Swami Ranganathananda (2002) links the soul of human beings with the super soul, the soul of divine beings. In his words: "the Supreme Soul is thus realized within oneself" (p. 16). In this context, the activities of human beings are also their *līlās* due to the realization of the Supreme Soul in them.

Līlā in the *Bhāgavata*, is related to the activities of the *Paurāṇic* characters. In this connection, Prahlāda discusses on Nṛsimha *līlā*. In his words:

As a snake captures a mouse or Garuḍa captures a very venomous snake, Lord Nṛsimhadeva captures Hiranyakaśipu, who could not be pierced even by the thunderbolt of King Indra. As Hiranyakaśipu moved his limbs here, there and all around, very much afflicted at being captured, Lord Nṛsimhadeva placed the demon on His lap, supporting him with His thighs, and in the doorway of the assembly hall the Lord very easily tore the demon to pieces with the nails of His hand². (7.8:29)

The above stanza is an example of Nṛsimha *Līlā* in which the divine being appears as Nṛsimha to rescue Prahlāda from the oppression of his demonic father Hiranyakaśipu. This *līlā* indicates the victory of truth and justice over injustice. In this context, Prabhupāda (2012) confirms that Nṛsimhadeva "easily killed the great demon Hiranyakaśipu" (p.443). This incarnation of Nṛsimha denotes the importance of god's *līlā* for well-being of creatures and to control oppressors on the earth.

With all the above logical descriptions, one concludes that Śūkadeva, Sūta, Brahmā,

Uddhava, Sage Maitreya and Prahlāda highlight the significance of *līlā* of divine beings in the universe for the establishment of righteousness, justice and peace. In the same way, Śrī Kṛṣṇa performs his playful activities for the sake of others and to maintain justice and peace in Vraha Bhumī. This idea further proves that the *Bhāgavata* discusses *līlās* of the divine characters but not the activities of common human beings.

Problems, Objectives, and Methodology

The Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa's portrayal of the *līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's presents interpretative challenges because of its blend of historical narrative and the elements of myth. The ethical implications of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's actions within his *līlā*, such as his playful mischief as a child, his romantic dalliances with the *gopīs* raise questions about the relationship between divine conduct and the morality of humans. In this study, the researcher tries his best to answer the following Research Questions:

- What *līlā* does Śrī Kṛṣṇa play in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*?
- How does Śrī Kṛṣṇa perform his *līlās* in the text?
- Why does Śrī Kṛṣṇa display his *līlās* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*?

The major objectives of this study are to explore the *līlās* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa; to analyze the ways of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās*, and to evaluate Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlās* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*.

To uncover Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*, the researcher uses *līlā* theory of Śrīla Sanātana Gosvāmī. In the perspective of the theorist: "Playful activities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa are his *līlās*" (3). The theorist strengthens that more complicated problems are supposed to be common for Śrī Kṛṣṇa and he solves difficult problems without any hurdles in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. Transliteration method has been used while citing examples from those texts except A.C. Bhaktivedanta Swāmī Prabhupada's the

Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa in English with Sanskrit stanzas. While citing examples, non-English words have been written in *italics* along with the translation of Prabhupāda in English from Sanskrit within inverted commas.

Review of Literature

A large number of philosophers, commentators, interpreters, scholars and researchers have interpreted the playful activities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa from multiple perspectives. Among various reviews, the researcher mentions the reviews of different critics and scholars about the *Yogic* Power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. Kṛṣṇa's *yogic* power is the next aspect of his life that highlights his activities. *Yoga* is an "attention in the control of the physical body that can be gained by long practice of its physical disciplines" (qtd. in Sivananda 1996: 1). It signifies the union of an individual soul with the universal consciousness. John Stratton Hawley (1981) associates the ideas from the *Bhāgavata* about the *Yogā* of Kṛṣṇa: "*Yogā* devotes specific attention to integrating (or, use the cognate term, yoking) what is complex; it defines a graded process; it emphasizes knowledge and practice; it is thought of mature and difficult" (p. 6). To support this idea, one can opine that *yogā* is a practical knowledge for the solution of difficult problems and Kṛṣṇa applies his *Yogic* power for the solution of diverse problems.

With the help of this power, he overcomes the crisis in his life. Prabhupāda (2012) explains and extends the *yogic* power of Kṛṣṇa: "Being, therefore, the ultimate object of *yoga*, Kṛṣṇa's name is *Yogesvara*, the master of *Yoga*" (p. 1) in the *Bhāgavata*. Kṛṣṇa is the base of the *yogic* power from which he performs the miraculous activities such as creating calves and cowherd boys, devouring the bonfire, multiplication of his own form during the time of his divine dance with the *gopīs*. It is in need of the spiritual practice for a person to remain perfect

in the *yogā*. Miraculous *yogic* power of Kṛṣṇa draws the attention of writers, philosophers, scholars and commentators. They have contributed their views to extend the *yogic* power of Kṛṣṇa. Major commentators, scholars and writers who have interpreted on this aspect of Kṛṣṇa are Prabhupāda, Sārthā Darśinī, Loknath Swami, Śrī Aurobindo, Benjamin Preciado- Solis, and Devi Dayal Aggarwal.

One can realize the *Yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa when Brahmā has stolen all the calves and the cowherd boys to test the power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. He knows the trick of Brahmā and "expanded Himself as calves and boys" (Prabhupāda 2012: 675). The superhero expands himself into missing calves and the cowherd boys with their exact bodily features which surprises Brahmā. It is the miraculous activity of Śrī Kṛṣṇa from his *Yogic* power. Sārathā Darśini (2011) supports Prabhupāda and she links this *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa with *mahat-tattva* [element]. In this connection, she claims: "To give bliss to Lord Brahma and the mothers, Kṛṣṇa expanded Himself into both the calves and the boys. Kṛṣṇa could do this because He is the master of *mahat-tattva* and the creator of the entire cosmic manifestation" (p. 327). *Mahat-tattva* is *budhi* (knowledge) from which there is the perfection of *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. Brahmā tries to bewilder Śrī Kṛṣṇa by hiding calves and boys but he himself is bewildered from the *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa because of the replacement of Śrī Kṛṣṇa into the cowherd boys and their calves in their respective places.

Loknath Swami (1998) extends the *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa: "He expanded and in matter no time there were as many cowherd boys as many he had that day coming with him herding the cows" (p. 4). This type of miraculous implementation of the *yogic* power cannot be found in the characters of the other heroes and superheroes in the history of the world-myth (Prabhupāda 2012: 675). On the base of this logic, one can opine that the power of the *yogā* can be utilized for fulfillment of multiple tasks. But the practicality of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's *yogic* power is beyond description in

words. The hero saves the family members of the cowherd boys' and cows from the fear of losing their members from their families. Other human and devine beings do not know the use of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's *yogic* power for this replacement except Brahmā.

Śrī Aurobindo (2012) has different argument in interrelation to the *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa: "If you meet Godhead there, it is not as a separate person; you feel only the Divine having a particular face, as it were, and interrelation with you for a certain purpose" (p. 458). The word "Godhead" traces Kṛṣṇa and his playful activities (Prabhupāda xv). Śrī Aurobindo regards Śrī Kṛṣṇa as a divine being having the face of a human with the *yogic* power to deal with crisis in his life. The use of the *yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa identifies him as the creator of this universe and to create the cowherd boys and calves in the forest of Vṛndāvana from his *yogic* power is an illustration of creation.

Benjamin Preciado-Solis (1984), a Mexican commentator on the *yogic* power of Kṛṣṇa, says: "The Lord of the lords of *yoga*, having heard their lamenting, smiling compassionately, though delighting [only] in [his own divine] self, gave intense delight to the *gopīs*" (p. 85). He regards Kṛṣṇa's intention to multiply himself into many numbers is to please to the *gopīs* during the time of *Rāsa Līlā*. One can argue that Kṛṣṇa does not only use his *yogic* power to save flora and fauna from crisis but also for the pleasure of the *gopīs*. Devi Dayal Aggrawal (1999) has different line of argument and focuses on different forms of Kṛṣṇa by regarding him as the Supreme Personality of Godhead but not as a human being (p. 196). Thus, a divine being can multiply as many numbers as he can as the need of time and situation.

The above review shows that there is perfection in the *yogic* power of Kṛṣṇa in the *Bhāgavata*. Firstly, Kṛṣṇa uses the *yogic* power to instruct Brahmā by replacing all the calves and the cowherd boys in their respective forms. Kṛṣṇa changes himself into the calves and the

cowherd boys. Secondly, he swallows the bonfire to keep calm to the fearful cowherd boys, animals and other creatures. Thirdly, Kṛṣṇa multiplies himself into different numbers to please the *gopīs*. Thus, Kṛṣṇa uses his *yogic* power for three times for different purposes to give a lesson to Brahmā, to save the cowherd community and to please the *gopīs* in the text.

Results and Discussions

Kinds of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* in the Śrīmad *Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*

The *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*, a revered text in the Hinduism, focuses on the divine play of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. It shows the playful activities on Śrī Kṛṣṇa's life, known as "Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā*", offer profound insights into the nature of divinity, human existence, and spiritual liberation. The results and discussions concerning Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* serve not only as a source of spiritual inspiration and guidance but also as a profound philosophical treatise on the nature of existence and the path to transcendence. Through the characters and events depicted in Śrī Kṛṣṇa's *Līlā*, the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* imparts valuable ethical and moral teachings, emphasizing virtues such as compassion, humility, honesty, and selflessness. It elucidates the concept of *māyā* (illusion) and the process of self-realization (*atma-jñāna*), wherein the individual soul awakens to its eternal identity and relationship with Śrī Kṛṣṇa.

The *Hindus* worship Śrī Kṛṣṇa, the eighth *avatār* of God Viṣṇu, as the Lord of love, compassion, and tenderness. He performs the different sorts of *līlās* according to the demand of time and situation. The Lord depicts His jocular and super human types of *līlās* which are not possible from an ordinary person. The super hero kills powerful demons either they are in the forms of animals and humans. The Lord has obligation to face the crisis which occur in his life. There are no choices in His

līlās. Osho (2015) argues: “Krishna is choiceless” (p. 43). Whatever the problems come in His life: the super hero accepts them happily. The Lord does not perform His *līlā* according to plans. The Lord faces all sorts of hurdles smilingly without any sign of hesitation. One finds the death of the most powerful demons from the hands of the Lord easily as a child who breaks dolls without any difficulties. There are four kinds of the major *līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa from his actions. In the words of Vanamali: These are *Bala Līlā*, *Rāsa Līlā*, *Raja Līlā*, and *Uttam Līlā* (4). Moving ahead in this line of logic, the analysis of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *Līlā* is highlighted as follows:

Bāla –Līlā

Bāla –Līlā of Śrī Kṛṣṇa as depicted in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* are some of the most endearing and enchanting stories of his divine activities. This *līlā* portrays him as the charming and playful divine child who enchants all with his innocence, wisdom, and love. The text narrates the miraculous birth of Śrī Kṛṣṇa in the prison of Kaṁsa in Mathura. In this connection Śūkadeva Gosvāmī corroborates:

Vasudeva then saw the newborn child, who had very wonderful lotus like eyes and who bore in His four hands the four weapons *ṣaṅkha*, *cakra*, *gadā* and *padma*. On His chest was the mark of *Ḍrēvatsa* and on His neck the brilliant *Kaustubha* gem. Dressed in yellow, His body blackish like a dense cloud.³ (10. 3:9)

The most agreeable factor concerning the matter is that the birth of Śrī Kṛṣṇa is different from the birth of other children. His birth includes a fascinating tale filled with divine significance. To strengthen the argument, Devdutt Pattanaik (2016) appraises: "The baby did not cry instead he smiled and gurgled with excitement" (p.34). This is often interpreted as a sign of his divine nature and his readiness to fulfill his purpose on Earth. It's a charming aspect of the story that adds to the miraculous and enchanting nature of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's birth.

To highlight *Bāla –Līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa, Śūkadeva incorporates his fighting with the demon

Ṭṇavarta evidence in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*:

Having assumed the form of a forceful whirlwind, the demon *Tāēāvarta* took

Kāñēa very high in the sky, but when *Kāñēa* became heavier than the demon, the demon had to stop his force and could go no further.⁴ (10. 7:26)

The aforementioned idea investigates a significant episode in Śrī Kṛṣṇa's childhood exploits. Śrī Kṛṣṇa's victory over *Ṭṇavarta* showcases his divine power even as a child, as well as his role as a protector of the righteous. This episode is often interpreted as a demonstration of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's divine mission to rid the world of evil forces and uphold righteousness. On the basis of this relation, Śrīla Sanātana Gosvāmī (2007) debunks that Śrī Kṛṣṇa is invincible in fighting (p.59). It shows that Śrī Kṛṣṇa possesses unparalleled strength, wisdom, and transcendental powers. His invincibility is not about overpowering others through brute force but rather about his unmatched righteousness, compassion, and divine grace.

One day, baby Śrī Kṛṣṇa is sleeping in bed at the house of Nanda Bābā. In this time, she-demon *Putanā*, an expert in infanticide comes to kill him feeding her breast with poison. But the child Śrī Kṛṣṇa kills her by sucking her blood. In this context, Śūkadeva argues logically mentioning the agony of *Putana* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*: “As *Putanā* screamed loudly and forcefully, the earth with its mountains, and outer space with its planets, trembled. The lover planets and all directions vibrated, and the people fell down, fearing that thunderbolts were falling upon them⁵ (10.6. 12). When Śrī Kṛṣṇa sucks the breast of *Putanā*, he simultaneously extracts her life force, causing her immense pain and ultimately leading to her demise. The intense pain and the shock of experiencing Śrī Kṛṣṇa's divine potency likely caused *Putanā* to scream as she faces her defeat and death. In the same line of argument, Ramesh Menon (2016) ponders that "Krishna fed at her breast and she died"

(p.744). This episode illustrates Śrī Kṛṣṇa's ability to protect his devotees and defeat evil forces, even as an infant. It serves as a reminder of the consequences that arise when one opposes or tries to harm the divine.

Likewise, Śrī Kṛṣṇa demonstrates his universal form as an important evidence of his *bāla līlā* to his mother Yaśodā in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. On the basis of this relation, sage Garga elucidates:

When Kāñēa opened his mouth wide by the order of mother Yaçodā, she saw within his mouth all moving and nonmoving entities, outer space, and all directions, along with mountains, islands, oceans, and the surface of the earth, the blowing wind, fire, the moon and the stars. She saw the planetary systems, water, light, air, sky, and creation by transformation of *ahaikāra*⁶. (10. 8: 37-38)

This event illustrates the concept of *līlā*, where Śrī Kṛṣṇa displays his Universal Form to his foster mother Yaçodā. To her astonishment, when she looks into his mouth, she sees the entire cosmos, including all the planets, stars, and galaxies, within Śrī Kṛṣṇa's mouth. Yasoda's reaction to witnessing this cosmic vision would likely be a mix of shock, awe, and a deepening of her love and reverence for Śrī Kṛṣṇa as her beloved son. On the basis of this idea, Prabhupāda (2012) writes ahead: "Because all these manifestations come from Govinda, they could all be visible within the mouth of Govinda" (p.471). It shows that Śrī Kṛṣṇa's universal form to Yasodā encapsulates the themes of love, devotion, divine play, and spiritual enlightenment, conveying profound insights into the nature of the divine-human relationship in the *Hindu* theology.

It is essential to reveal Śrī Kṛṣṇa's killing of the demon Aghāsura to expose his *līlā* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. Aghāsura is a serpent demon who takes the form of a giant python. He has a malicious intent to devour and his friends, the cowherd boys. Aghasura disguised himself as a massive cave, and out of curiosity, Śrī Kṛṣṇa and his friends enter the

cave, unaware of the danger. In Śūkadeva's words:

Then, because Kāñēa had increased the size of his body, the demon extended his own body to a very large size. Nonetheless, his breathing stopped, he suffocated, and his eyes rolled here and there and popped out. The demon's life air, however, could not pass through any outlet, and therefore it finally burst out through a hole in the top of the demon's head.⁷ (10. 12:31)

This extract encapsulates themes of divine supremacy, the insignificance of material power in the face of the divine, the inevitability of the defeat of evil, and the potential for spiritual liberation even for the most sinful beings. Explaining this statement, Mohan Kumar Pokhrel (2023) corroborates: "The precepts of Kṛṣṇa are reliable and useful for the decision makers" (32). It is interesting to note that the precepts of Śrī Kṛṣṇa provide a framework for leading a meaningful life. This episode highlights Śrī Kṛṣṇa's role as a protector of righteousness and his ability to vanquish evil forces.

Śrī Kṛṣṇa performs his miraculous activities by replacing cowherd boys and cows in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. Śūkadeva unveils this *līlā* in his statement: "In this way, Lord Çré Kāñēa, having himself become the cowherd boys and groups of calves, maintained himself by himself. Thus he continued his pastimes, both in Vāndāvana and in the forest, for one year"⁸ (10.13:27). This standpoint justifies the depth of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* due to replacement himself as each of the missing cowherd boys and calves. This divine play continues for a whole year in the earthly realm, during which Brahmā realizes his mistake and humbly approaches Śrī Kṛṣṇa, seeking forgiveness. Śrī Kṛṣṇa, in his magnanimity, reveals his true divine nature to Brahmā, and everything returns to its natural state. In this context, Sārātha Darśinī (2011) states that Śrī Kṛṣṇa himself becomes cowherd boys and groups of calves (p.334). Brahmā wants to surprise Śrī Kṛṣṇa by hiding cowherd boys and calves but he is surprised himself due

to the replacement of the cowherd boys and calves with the help of his *Yogic* Power.

The establishment of the new trend of worshipping Govardhan Hillock is the base of fury for Indra against Śrī Kṛṣṇa. In this context, Cornelia Dimmitt and J.A.B. Van Buitenen (2015) expose the fury of Indra and his order to *Samvartaka* cloud for the heavy rain (p.116). Concerning this argument, one can agree that the shifting of trend from Indra, the king of gods to Govardhan Hillock makes Indra pour the heavy rain at the area of Govardhan Hillock. The heavy rain is a typical example for the destructive form of Nature for the inhabitants of that place. Relating this incident, the *Śrimad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* portrays: "As the clouds released torrents of rain as thick as massive columns, the earth was submerged in the flood, and high ground could no longer be distinguished from low"⁹ (10. 25: 10). Rain symbolizes fertility and creation on the earth. But the heavy rain for a long time is destructive form of Nature. The wrath of Indra in the form of the heavy rain causes panic for Govardhana Hillock dwellers. In the *paurāṇic* period, it was the system to attack others using the *Yogic* power. Indra used his *Yogic* power for the origin of the heavy rain to create problems for the cowherd community.

The effect of the destructive form of Nature causes fear to human beings, birds, and animals. The *Śrimad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* refers the panic as the fearful visionary description as an occasional destructive form of Nature: "The cows and other animals, shivering from the excessive rain and wind, and the cowherd men and ladies, pained by the cold, all approached Lord Govinda for shelter"¹⁰ (10. 25: 11). Humans cannot remain free from the destructive form of Nature so that they need to be sensitive about it. During the time of destruction of Nature, it is our duty to protect as far as possible. If human beings destroy Nature, it may be their self-destruction so that this scenario of the text makes humans aware of Nature. The creatures and plants are victimized from the creation of flood by the wrath of Indra.

This condition shows that the wrath of Indra affects the life of the dwellers of Govardhan Hill. From this standpoint, Kamala Subramaniam (2013) expresses her view: "The cowherds, their wives, and children were helpless" (p. 462). The condition of the cowherd community was miserable at the beginning of the heavy rain. In this situation, the inhabitants of Govardhana Hill expected solution of the problem by Śrī Kṛṣṇa and they address him: "Kṛṣṇa, O most fortunate one, please deliver the cows from the wrath of Indra! O Lord, You are so affectionate to Your devotees"¹¹ (10. 25: 13). The cowherd community remembers Śrī Kṛṣṇa for help. Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* is in need for the inhabitants of that place for solution of the destructive form of Nature and they appeal him to help them. They know the miraculous power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa and request him to help.

Indra does not show mercy to the helpless condition of the cowherd community. Supporting this opinion, Kavi Karnapura (2016) claims that "Indra felt no fatigue as he continued to attack Giriraja" (p.161). In this line of logic, one can argue that Indra shows his fury in the form of the torrential rain. During this crisis, Śrī Kṛṣṇa uses his *Yogic* Power lifting up the Govardhan Hillock to make conscious to Indra. At this point, Śukadeva argues with evidence: "Śrī Kṛṣṇa picked up Govardhan Hill with one hand and held it aloft just as easily as a child holds up a mushroom"¹² (10. 25: 19). From this logic, one can express that the things of Nature are useful in the time of need either for benefits or to save us from crisis. This *līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa portrays the utility of natural things to save creatures. In this connection, Benjamin Preciado-Solis (1984) expresses his notion: ""The themes of a strong-man are found all through the life of Kṛṣṇa" (p.78). There is the link between *dharma* and *karma* from this *līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. From this standpoint, the argument in favor of Nature is plausible. From this *līlā*, Śrī Kṛṣṇa gives lesson to human beings to help others during the time of crisis.

Jayashree Venugopala (2000) elaborates that Kṛṣṇa lifts up the Govardha Hillock for one week and safeguards people and animals (p. 95). It shows that the act of Śrī Kṛṣṇa is miracle. In this regard, humans assume him as a mythical character with incredible strength. As a nature lover, it is his duty to protect cows and the cowherd community from the destructive form of Nature. The cowherd community shelters under the hillock and the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* states this scenario in this way: "Their minds thus pacified by Lord Kṛṣṇa, they all entered beneath the hill, where they found ample room for themselves and all their cows, wagons, servants and priests, and for all other members of the community as well"¹³ (10. 25: 22). The cowherd communities bring their domestic animals beneath the Govardhana Hill for safety. The use of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* to deal with the destructive form of Nature for protection of humans and the domestic animals is admirable. The role of animals is as important as the role of humans in ecology.

Govardhana Hillock is a remarkable Nature image in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* in which Śrī Kṛṣṇa plays his role as a philanthropist by rescuing humans and animal property. In the understanding of Pattanaik (2016) : "The story of Indra's defeat most clearly reveals a shift away from the *Vedic* worship of celestial beings to the more popular worship of Nature. Krishna was clearly a pastoral god who gradually became part of later *Puranic Hinduism*, overthrowing old *Vedic* gods" (p.92). Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* is part and parcel to save human beings and other creatures from crisis. As a philanthropist, he solves the complicated problems easily. The help of Śrī Kṛṣṇa to the inhabitants of the Govardhana Hillock is a model to humans how to help others while they are suffering from natural disaster. Thus, in this context, Śrī Kṛṣṇa teaches human beings how to deal with the natural disaster in the world as the circumstances.

Śrī Kṛṣṇa's childhood in Gokula is marked by his playful and mischievous activities. He

performs various miraculous activities such as defeating demons sent by Kāṁsa to kill him. Throughout his childhood, Śrī Kṛṣṇa imparts timeless wisdom through his interactions and teachings. The *Bāla Līlā* of Kṛṣṇa in the *Bhāgavata Purāna* is not just a collection of enchanting tales but also serves as a spiritual guide, inspiring devotees to cultivate love, devotion, and righteousness in their lives. Śrī Kṛṣṇa's childhood stories in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* often marks the transition to his adulthood, where he begins to fulfill his purpose as a leader, teacher, and warrior. Thus, *Sri Kṛṣṇa Līlā* serves to inspire devotion, illustrate the power of divine grace, and provide moral and spiritual guidance to devotees.

Rāsa Līlā

The *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* discusses *Rāsa Līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa with *gopīs* of Vraja in five chapters (twenty nine to thirty three) of the tenth *skandha* (canto). To make *Rāsa Līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa with *gopīs* more informative, Monier Williams further explores: "*Rāsa* is the dance of one male with several females"(qtd in Solis 1984: 84). Supporting this logic, one can expose that *Rāsa Līlā* is the sporting of Śrī Kṛṣṇa with several *gopīs* in which he remains in centre to please all of them. It is an interesting playful activity of Śrī Kṛṣṇa in which there is the involvement of a large number of *gopīs* (qtd in Fillion 2018: 504). It takes place during the time of the full moon night in the forest of Vṛndāvana. The readers of *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* require predisposition for the rapture from this *līlā* of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. Rapture, a part of *bhaktirāsa*, is brought by transcendental potency. The *Rāsa Līlā* has its connection to Nature for its utility to human beings and other creatures. It shows how there is attraction between *Prakṛīti* and *Purūsa*. Śūkadeva deals with beauty of Nature: "Śrī Kṛṣṇa is the Supreme Personality of Godhead, full in all opulence, yet upon seeing those autumn nights scented with blossoming jasmine flowers, He turned His mind toward loving affairs"¹⁴ (10. 29: 1). Richness in Natural beauty motivates Śrī Kṛṣṇa dance with

gopīs in forest. Śrī Kṛṣṇa has intention to link the beauty of Nature to the beauty of the *gopīs*. In a similar note, it is crucial to remember the amalgamation of the natural beauty with the beauty of women. In this connection, Swāmī Sivananda (1996) argues that he was cupid for *gopīs* (p. 19). He arranges to provide them everlasting peace and bliss during the time of *Rāsa Līlā* at night in the forest of Vṛndāvana. It indicates the proofs in the perfection of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *līlā* by arranging *Rāsa Līlā*.

Śrī Kṛṣṇa uses his power of *Yogamāyā* to make impossible things possible in the shelter of forest. This argument turns out to be valid when Śrī Kṛṣṇa "defeats the vanity of Cupid" (qtd in Filion 2018: 20). There is harmony in the *Rāsa* dance with the beauty of Nature and Śrī Kṛṣṇa enjoys with *gopīs*. The moon is a significant component of Natural beauty, has her crucial role in the *Rāsa Līlā*. This idea, further, points to the reality: "The moon rose, anointing the face of the eastern horizon with the reddish hue of his comforting rays, and thus dispelling the pain of all who watched him rise"]¹⁵ (10. 29: 2). The moon seems to be a lover who stares to his beloved after a long time and raises her emotions. The rising moon inspires Śrī Kṛṣṇa to originate the mood for union with *gopīs*. The aforementioned expression creates the background of "jungle *mein mangal*" (qtd. in Pattanaik 2016: 17) for both Śrī Kṛṣṇa and *gopīs*.

Unlike Filion and Pattanaik, David Kinsley expresses the power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's magical flute in the forest for the background of *Rāsa Līlā*:

The sound of Kṛṣṇa's flute is no earthly sound. Its vibrations fill the heavens and distract even the gods from their usual activities. Even nature cannot remain unaffected. When he plays his flute, the river and the reeds from which the flute grew weep tears of delight. When the clouds hear his flute, they hover over him to provide the shade and shower him with drops of fresh water. Rivers slow down when they hear his flute and grow lotuses for him. (172)

The magical music of the flute's motion creates feelings of closeness for natural things. The rivers, reeds, and clouds are attracted listening the music. Both plants and animals lose their patience and they are distracted from their normal activities. The *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* presents sufficient evidences of *Rāsa Līlā* in the background with the manifestation of Nature.

In the autumn, Śrī Kṛṣṇa enters into the forest of Vṛndāvana with cows. Jasmine, *kumuda*, *kunkuma* flowers are blossoming there. Śūkadeva presents the background from melodious sound of his flute:

Kṛṣṇa saw the unbroken disk of the moon glowing with the red effulgence of newly applied vermilion, as if it were the face of the goddess of fortune. He also saw the *kumuda* and lotuses opening in response to the moon's presence and the forest gently illumined by its rays. Thus, Kṛṣṇa began to play sweetly on his flute, attracting the minds of the beautiful-eyed *gopīs*.¹⁶ (10. 29: 3)

The moon, which originates the mood of Śrī Kṛṣṇa for romance, has prominent role for preparation of the *rāsa* dance. It motivates him to play the flute during the time of this happy moment. In relation to this idea, Muhammad Khan (2013) further explains his points: "The flute is the human heart, a heart which is made hollow, which becomes a flute for the god of love to play" (p. 4). This discussion hints that the heart of human beings should be emptied to help others. As the sound of the flute, one should try to please others as far as possible. From the perspective of the flute, one can argue that hollowness of the flute symbolizes simplicity.

The melodious sound from the music of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's flute arouses desires of the world due to its attraction to plants and animals. Everybody stops his/her work during the time of listening the sound. Similarly, the wives of demigods stop their works from the impression of the sound. With this conditioning, Śūkadeva expresses: "The wives of the demigods, observing Śrī Kṛṣṇa's playful activities were

entranced and became agitated with lust. Indeed, even the moon and his entourage, the stars, became astonished"¹⁷ (10. 33: 18). Women and the objects of Nature such as the moon and stars are affected by the sound of Kṛṣṇa's flute. There is accompanying of Nature with the sound of his flute. Explaining this statement, David Kingsley (1998) further elucidates: "A bamboo flute is the only musical instrument which is most natural and does not contain any mechanical parts. This is the reason why the flute is very close to nature"(p. 32). The echo sound of the flute is delightful for creatures. The flute player might realize the celestial experiences.

The simplicity of the flute is the sign of simple and cooperative activities of human beings. In this regard, Bhattacharya (1947) supports Kingsley about the utility of the flute of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. He extends the scope of the flute from his following argument: "The flute has eight holes, using which divine music is brought out by the player. Eight is number of Indian god Kṛṣṇa; the eight holes control the eight parts of the body and mind: eyes, ears, nose, tongue, skin, mind, intellect, and ego" (p. 21). The flute has its spiritual importance in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. It reveals common lifestyle of human beings. The music of the flute attracts *gopīs* to Śrī Kṛṣṇa for the performance of the *Rāsa Līlā*. A person should be as a hollow flute in the absence of vanity to whom everybody likes.

Rāsaṅcādhyāyī (five chapters) enthuse the profound devotion and bitter scorn in the character of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. In Jarow's (2003) word: "In *Rāsa Līlā*, the world of *māyā*, is about to be turned upside down" (p. 98). With the support of this idea, one can debunk that Śrī Kṛṣṇa is criticised despite his dedication to rescue good humans of his contemporary time. Moving ahead in this line of logic, Śukadeva rightly argues about the position of Śrī Kṛṣṇa and *gopīs* in the *rāsa* dance:

Among the assembled *gopīs*, the infallible Lord Kṛṣṇa appeared just like the moon surrounded by stars. He whose activities are so

magnanimous made their faces blossom with His affectionate glances, and His broad smiles revealed the effulgence of His jasmine-bud-like teeth.¹⁸ (*Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* 10. 29: 43)

Śrī Kṛṣṇa seizes the minds of *gopīs* and they participate in the *Rāsa Līlā* having suspended their works. They have unchained themselves from the attachment of family. In reality, there are moral issues of women to leave home at night but the *gopīs* neglect ethics and the moral issues. In the theistic mode, Richa Pauranik Clements (2002) incorporates: "[*Gopīs* are *tāmas* devotees, and for them Kṛṣṇa is no more than an irresistible lover"] (p. 129). This analysis shows that they are hunger for physical proximity and have intention to make a union with him.

In *Rāsa Līlā*, Śrī Kṛṣṇa pleases *gopīs* from his songs, dance, and music using the flute. By indicating the way of his dance, Śukadeva informs king Parīkṣit:

There Kṛṣṇa threw His arms around the *gopīs* and embraced them. He aroused Cupid in the beautiful young ladies of Vraja by touching their hands, hair, thighs, belts and breasts, playfully scratching them with His fingernails, and also by joking with them, glancing at them and laughing with them. In this way, the Lord enjoyed His Pastimes.¹⁹ (10. 29: 46)

The *Yogic* power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa takes place "out of time and out of mind" (qtd. in Jarow 2003:114) to make impossible works possible. There is the depiction of attachment and cleverness in the commencement of this *rāsa* dance. He hugs the *gopīs* from the extension of his arms and they have the realization of bliss. In this context, McKim Marriott (1966) confirms "Krishna's miraculous and amorous boyhood" (p. 201) from this performance. Due to his *Rāsa Līlā* with *gopīs*, Śrī Kṛṣṇa turns from childhood to boyhood. He knows the techniques to please *gopīs* during the time of *Rāsa Līlā* and proves himself as a perfect lover.

Gopīs realize good fortune to get Śrī Kṛṣṇa as a lover. In this relation, Śrī Kṛṣṇa proves himself as a womanizer during the time of his

adolescence. During the time of the *rāsa* dance, some *gopīs* including Vṛṣabhanu-
 nandinī try to possess Śrī Kṛṣṇa for them (Filion 236) and become jealous each other. Śrī
 Kṛṣṇa realizes possessive psychology of the *gopīs*. Then, he persuades: "just climb on my
 shoulder." But as soon as He said this, He disappeared. His beloved consort then
 immediately felt great remorse"²⁰ (10. 30: 38). This evidence proves defeat of lust in Platonic
 Love. Rādhā shows anguish during *rāsa* dance. To please Rādhā and to make *gopīs* free
 from jealousy each others, Śrī Kṛṣṇa disappears. Solis (1984) gives reason why the
gopīs are attracted with Śrī Kṛṣṇa: "the *gopīs* dance around Śrī Kṛṣṇa, giving him the place
 of the original phallic symbol" (p. 84). Readers analyze that phallus is the sign of
 attraction for women and the condition of *gopīs* is same. For Śrī Kṛṣṇa, the *Rāsa Līlā* is
 not possessive but pleasing for creatures and vegetation. Śrī Kṛṣṇa is against the possessive
 love which is flourished in the life of human beings. Sudden disappearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa
 indicates that he has self-awareness and wants to detach from the sensual pleasure. But the
 case of *gopīs* contradicts from the condition of Śrī Kṛṣṇa on the basis of the *rāsa* dance. They
 have their desires to have continuation in their dance and do not like to be separated from him.
 In this regard, one can appraise if there is union between soul and senses for a short time, the
 soul tries to remain free but senses run after pleasure (qtd. in Filion 2018:72). The reality is
 that the soul should guide the senses for good deeds. Sudden disappearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa
 from *gopīs* is justifiable in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*.

The minds of *gopīs* have fully absorbed in ideas of Śrī Kṛṣṇa and they start looking for
 him everywhere in forest. Their climax of bliss shatters from the disappearance of their
 consort. Filion (2018) confirms: "Śrī Kṛṣṇa disappeared for the sake of special bliss" (p.
 319). He knows that absence in love increases its frequency during the time of reunion. On
 the basis of this relation, Śūkadēva focuses on the psychology of *gopīs*: "When Lord Kṛṣṇa

disappears, the *gopīs* suffered in His absence. Their condition is as the condition of the
 female elephants from the loss of their mate"²¹ (10. 30: 1). This discussion reflects analogy of
 the *gopīs* to the female elephants during the time of separation. In relation to this idea, one
 postulates that human beings have qualities of animals according to time and situation. A
 human has the characteristics of different animals and the *gopīs* show the quality of the
 female elephants during the time of separation. From this standpoint, Purnendu Narayana
 Sinha (1901) argues: "They gave up their search when it was dark" (p. 419). Explaining
 this statement, one argues that dark night creates obstacle for *gopīs* to search Śrī Kṛṣṇa.
 In this context, dark night is a component of Nature and it is superior to humans. The *gopīs*
 cannot do anything against it in the dense forest.

The *gopīs* love passionately to Śrī Kṛṣṇa and they feel emptiness in the absence of him.
 They rest on the argument that the plants and trees know where Śrī Kṛṣṇa is and start asking
 questions to trees. Tagare (2007) formulates his logic with the sufficient evidences to show
 the psychology of *gopīs* when they personify the trees by asking them:

Oh mango tree! Oh jackfruit tree, apple tree, the sun plant, the wood- apple tree, *Kadamba*
 and *Nipa* and other trees on the bank of the Yamuna-Born as you are for the benefit of
 others! May you direct the path of Kṛṣṇa to use whose minds are vacant due to separation from
 Hari. (p. 1444)

It is an evidence of the idyllic state of youth from the above manifestation of the *gopīs*'s
 situation. The *gopīs* have their queries for reunion with Śrī Kṛṣṇa to quench their thirst of
 love. They realize the futility in effort to identify his location even though they "do not
 die of separation" (qtd. in Jarow 2003: 110). They have their illusion thinking that the
 objects of Nature may help for the solution of their problems. Positive attitude towards trees
 becomes the base of consolation for *gopīs* during the time of separation.

Prabhupāda explores that “*gopīs* felt that the trees had not replied because they were male”²² (10: 30. 7). The same trees, rivers, birds, and animals which had pleased them in the presence of Śrī Kṛṣṇa, make them unhappy during the time of his absence. From the activities of *gopīs*, one can corroborate that human psychology is very important to gain pain and pleasure from same object. If a person is unhappy due to some psychological problems, he cannot be happy in the place of beautiful scenario of Nature as *gopīs*.

The analysis of the text discussed in this context indicates that the *gopīs* express the sign of jealousy to creepers. On the basis of this relation, Śūkadeva appraises: "Let us ask these creepers about Śrī Kṛṣṇa. Even though they are embracing the arms of their husband, this tree, they certainly must have been touched by Śrī Kṛṣṇa's fingernails, since out of joy they are manifesting eruptions on their skin"²³ (10. 30: 13). The above discussion shows that the *gopīs* lose the sense of their judgement due to the ailment of their lust. This state of sorrow of the *gopīs* asserts their stressful condition at night. In the same line of argument, Devi Dayal Aggarwal (1999) points out that being favorite of all, Śrī Kṛṣṇa has stolen the heart of everyone. He is therefore a *chittachor* (p. 173). The heart is the most sensitive organ of human body and Śrī Kṛṣṇa steals the hearts of those persons who are sensitive in their feelings. Nature affects the *gopīs* negatively and they regard it as selfish and uncooperative to share their sympathy and empathy.

The love of *gopīs* turns into *bhakti* (devotion) due to their emotional attachment with Śrī Kṛṣṇa and they go to the Yamunā River to pray him. In this connection, David. L. Haberman (2006) exposes: "Yamunā Devī initiates into the world of divine love the soul of those who bathe in and drink her water, and unites them with Kṛṣṇa" (p. 347). Expecting for the reunion with Śrī Kṛṣṇa, the *gopīs* start singing songs. *Gopī-gītā* relates to the transcendental pain of separation of *gopīs*. The songs of love-stricken *gopīs* highlight the glory of Śrī Kṛṣṇa to forget

pain of separation in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. According to *gopīs*:

O beloved, Your birth in the land of Vraja has made it exceedingly glorious, and thus Indirā, the goddess of fortune, always resides here. It is only for Your sake that we, Your devoted servants, maintain our lives. We have been searching everywhere for You, so please show Yourself to us²⁴ (10. 31: 1)

This discussion is related to the qualities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa for the motivation of *gopīs*. It reflects intolerable agony of *gopīs* during the time of separation. For them, Vraja is more glorious than Vaikuntha because of the performance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's *Rāsa Līlā*.

For *gopīs*, their lover is the embodiment of *śṛṅgāra-rasa*- feeling of beauty and they have agitation to see his presence. Basing this interpretation, Prabhupāda (2012) argues: "They expect eagerly that Kṛṣṇa will come to meet them again. It shows that the *gopīs* want to continue *Rāsa Līlā* of Kṛṣṇa. The *geet* relieves the agony of those suffering from the burning pain of separation from Kṛṣṇa and which bestows supreme consciousness" (p. 611). It reflects queries of *gopīs* for the memory of Śrī Kṛṣṇa in their maddened condition of separation. For the sake of consolation, as the *gopīs* start singing the song, their role changes from beloveds to devotees. They are really good devotees who leave their houses for the sake of Śrī Kṛṣṇa.

Keeping the love of Śrī Kṛṣṇa in hearts, the *gopīs* express their nostalgia as follows: "When You leave the cowherd village to herd the cows, our minds are disturbed with the thought that Your feet, more beautiful than a lotus, will be pricked by the spiked husks of grain and the rough grass and plants"²⁵ (10. 31: 11). This discussion oscillates that the *gopīs* do not like to see and hear the pain of Śrī Kṛṣṇa during the time of tending cows in the pasture of Vraja. They are sensitive not to hurt him from any natural objects when he is far from them. On the basis of this relation, Richa Pauranik Clements (2002) is apt to state that "In the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Purāṇa*, *viraha*

bhakti is primarily associated with the *gopīs*" (p. 136). With the similar beliefs, human beings know that the *gopīs* are worried about the obstacles that Kṛṣṇa faces in forest. From this evidence, one can declare that the *gopīs* are worried too much about Śrī Kṛṣṇa than their lives.

There is the fulfilment of eagerness of the *gopīs* when Śrī Kṛṣṇa appears among them again in a silken yellow garment with a flower garland. From his presence, the pain *gopīs* have felt from his separation is dispelled. The *gopīs* remark that Śrī Kṛṣṇa understands their agony during the time of his absence. From the presence of Śrī Kṛṣṇa, the *gopīs* forget their anxieties and remain happy with his company. As Śrī Kṛṣṇa comes to the bank of the Yamunā River, they make a seat for him using their shawls. Due to excessive devotion of those *gopīs*, there is the reappearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa among them which is a matter of ecstasy for them. In this regard, Śūkadeva discusses the appearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa: "One *gopī* respects Kṛṣṇa in her eyes and places Him within her heart. Having closed her eyes, the thirsty *gopī* of love embraces Him within. The *gopī* has the realization of the transcendental ecstasy meditating upon the Lord"²⁶ (10. 32: 8). This discussion reveals the suppressed emotions of the love-lorn *gopīs*. With this conditioning, it shows that the *gopīs* are portrayed as the ornaments of Śrī Kṛṣṇa to highlight his character. The appearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa makes the *gopīs* worship him both physically and mentally. The presence of Śrī Kṛṣṇa embalms the injured hearts of the *gopīs* and they express their love from their eyes, hearts, and activities. They tolerate sorrows but do not make any inconvenience for him. They love both Nature and Śrī Kṛṣṇa without any sign of complaints. In this regard, Śrīnāth Paṇḍita proves that "Kṛṣṇa is the soul, the topmost *Purūsa*" (qtd. in Fillion 2018: 96). Being *nirguṇa*, Śrī Kṛṣṇa engages in romance with the divine *gopīs* (qtd. in Fillion 2018: 110). The moment of reunion is the base of bliss for the sake of the *gopīs*.

Śūkadeva proves that the *gopīs* forget their distress of separation from the sudden appearance of Śrī Kṛṣṇa among them. For them, Śrī Kṛṣṇa is the goal and substance in their lives and they feel great relief from his reappearance. The beauty and purity of Nature creates background of reunion for them. The sage further exemplifies the reality:

The almighty Lord then took the *gopīs* with Him to the bank of the Kālindī, who with the handle of her waves had scattered piles of soft sand upon the shore. In that auspicious place, the breeze, bearing the fragrance of blooming *kunda* and *mandāra* flowers, attracted many bees.²⁷ (10. 32: 12)

In this context, Nature is the most visible aspect for the clarification of the *Rāsa Līlā* in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*. With this conditioning, Hanumanprasād Poddar (2010) presents sufficient evidences about Śrī Kṛṣṇa's dance in Vrindāvana: "It was through the influence of *Yogamāyā* that Śrī Kṛṣṇa when He was only a child of seven years appeared as a grown up lad to the eyes of the damsels of Vraja" (p. 53). With the help of influence from his *Yogamāyā*, he plays the sports of *rāsa* dance. The night time with beautiful scenario of forest plays a crucial role as the background for the *Rāsa Līlā*.

The base of Śrī Kṛṣṇa *caritra* is the eagerness of mind and independence of thoughts. These opinions further point to the reality from the statement of Śūkadeva referring the scenario of the *rāsa* dance: "The festive *rāsa* dance commenced, with the *gopīs* arrayed in a circle. Lord Kṛṣṇa expanded Himself and entered between each pair of *gopīs*, and as that master of mystic power placed His arms around their necks, each girl thought He was standing next to her alone"²⁸ (10. 33: 3). This idea is the ultimate implementation of the *Yogic* Power of Śrī Kṛṣṇa. It should be appraised that dance is the point of focus for the *gopīs* but not Śrī Kṛṣṇa (qtd. in Jarow 2003:115). To strengthen the argument, Devdutt Pattanaik incorporates his idea that at the beginning of the *rāsa* dance, Śrī Kṛṣṇa had a single form. Then, he

disappears and appears again and multiplies himself into many forms (p. 98). It is an incredible matter for readers to believe that a person changes into different forms as the time of need. His work is as the works of a magician in front of the *gopīs*. It hints that Śrī Kṛṣṇa makes impossible works possible from his *yogic* power.

The analysis of the above discussion traces that the *Rāsa Līlā* "is a meeting of contradictory forces, and that all its happiness comes from this union of the opposites" (qtd. in Osho 2015: 256). It is related to the union between the energies of male and female for creation. On the base of this argument, one realizes the union between *Prakṛiti* (female energy) and *Puruṣa*-male energy. Without the union of these two opposite energies, there is no creation in this world. This divine dance symbolizes the flow of male and female attraction. The attraction between the two opposite forces is inevitable for the existence of the creation of plants and animals. In the similar vein, there is the existence of planets and stars in the universe from the existence of the opposite forces (qtd. in Osho 2015: 260). From the *Rāsa Līlā*, human beings come to the conclusion that attraction between a man and a woman is necessary because there is no completion between them in the absence of another.

Conclusion

In the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa*, *Bāla Līlā* and *Rāsa Līlā* are two significant narratives that portray the playful activities of Śrī Kṛṣṇa during his childhood and youth respectively. *Bāla Līlā* focuses on Śrī Kṛṣṇa's childhood activities in Vṛndāvan, depicting his playful interactions with the cowherd boys and his endearing relationship with his devotees, especially the *gopīs*. These stories are filled with innocence, mischief, and the charm of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's divine persona as a child. In the similar vein, *Rāsa Līlā* delves into Śrī Kṛṣṇa's romantic dalliances with the *gopīs*, particularly the enchanting dance he performs with them in

the moonlit nights of Vṛndāvan. This divine dance symbolizes the ultimate union of the individual soul (*jīva*) with the supreme soul (*paramātmā*) and is often interpreted allegorically to represent the soul's longing for union with the divine.

Both *Bāla Līlā* and *Rāsa Līlā* are imbued with profound spiritual symbolism and serve as metaphors for the soul's journey towards union with the divine. *Bāla Līlā* highlights the sweetness of devotion and the innocence of love, while *Rāsa Līlā* explores the depths of divine love and the mystical union between the individual soul and the Supreme Being. These narratives in the *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Mahāpurāṇa* are not merely stories of Śrī Kṛṣṇa's playful romantic escapades, but rather profound allegories that convey thoughtful spiritual truths about the nature of love, devotion, and the ultimate goal of human existence and the union with the divine.

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Appendix

1. प्रयुक्तान् भोजराजेन मायिनः कामरूपिणः ।

लीलया व्यनुदत्तांस्तान् बालः क्रीडनकानिव ॥ ३० ॥ (3.2:30)

*prayuktān bhoja-rājena
māyinaḥ kāma-rūpiṇaḥ
līlaya vyanudat tāms tān
bālaḥ krīḍanakān iva*

2. विष्वक्स्फुरन्तं ग्रहणातुरं हरिव्यालो

यथाऽऽखुं कुलिशाक्षतत्वचम् ।

द्वार्यूर आपात्य ददार लीलया

नखैर्यथाहिं गरुडो महाविषम् ॥ २९ ॥ (7.8:29)

*viṣvak sphurantam grahaṇāturaṁ harir
vyālo yathākhuṁ kulīśākṣata-tvacam
dvāry ūrum āpatya dadāra līlayā
nakhair yathāhiṁ garuḍo mahā-viṣam*

3. तमद्भुतं बालकमम्बुजेक्षणं

चतुर्भुजं शङ्खगदाद्युदायुधम् ।

श्रीवत्सलक्ष्मं गलशोभिकौस्तुभं

पीताम्बरं सान्द्रपयोदसौभगम् ॥ ९ ॥ (10.3:9)

*tam adbhutaṁ bālakam ambujekṣaṅgāṁ
catur-bhujaṁ ṣaṅkha-gadādy-udāyudham
śrīvatsa-lakṣmaṁ gala-ṣobhi-kaustubhaṁ
pētāmbaraṁ sāndra-payoda-saubhagam*

4. तृणावर्तः शान्तरयो वात्यारूपधरो हरन् ।

कृष्णं नभो गतो गन्तुं नाशक्नोद्भूरिभारभृत् ॥ २६ ॥ (10.7:26)

*tāḍāvartaḥ śāntarayo vātyā-rūpa-dharo haran
kṛṣṇaṁ nabho-gato gantuṁ nāṣaknod bhūri-bhāra-bhṛt*

5. तस्याः स्वनेनातिगभीरं हसा

साद्रिर्मही द्यौश्च चचाल सग्रहा ।

रसा दिशश्च प्रतिनेदिरे जनाः

पेतुः क्षितौ वज्रनिपातशङ्कया ॥ १२ ॥ (10.6:12)

*tasyäù svanenätigabhéra-raàhasä
sädrir mahé dyauç ca cacäla sa-grahä
rasä diçaç ca pratinedire janäù
petuù kñitau vajra-nipäta-çaikayä*

6. सा तत्र ददृशे विश्वं जगत्स्थास्नु च खं दिशः ।

साद्रिद्वीपाब्धिभूगोलं स वाय्वग्नीन्दुतारकम् ॥ ३७ ॥

ज्योतिश्चक्रं जलं तेजो नभस्वान् वियदेव च ।

वैकारिकाणीन्द्रियाणि मनो मात्रा गुणास्त्रयः ॥ ३८ ॥ (10.8: 37-38)

*sä tatra dadåçe viçvaàjagat sthäsnu ca khaà diçaù
sädri-dvépäbdhi-bhügolaàsa-väyv-agnéendu-täarakam
jyotiç-cakraà jalaà tejonabhasvån viyad eva ca
vaikärikäëéndriyääi mano mäträ guëäs trayau*

7. ततोऽतिकायस्य निरुद्धमार्गिणो

ह्युद्गीर्णदृष्टेर्भ्रमतस्त्वितस्ततः ।

पूर्णेऽन्तरङ्गे पवनो निरुद्धो

मूर्धन् विनिष्पाट्य विनिर्गतो बहिः ॥ ३१ ॥ (10. 12: 31)

*tato 'tikäyasya niruddha-märgiëo
hy udgérëa-dãñöer bhramatas tv itas tataù
pürëo 'ntar-aige pavano niruddho
mürdhan vinirbhidya vinirgato bahiù*

8. इत्थमात्माऽऽत्मनाऽऽत्मानं वत्सपालमिषेण सः ।

पालयन् वत्सपो वर्षं चिक्रीडे वनगोष्ठयोः ॥ २७ ॥ (10.13: 27)

*ittham ätmätmanätmänää vatsa-päla-miñëëa saù
pälayan vatsapo varñää cikréöe vana-goñöhayou*

9. एवमुक्तः प्रियामाह स्कन्ध आरुह्यतामिति ।

ततश्चान्तर्दधे कृष्णः सा वधूरन्वतप्यत ॥ ३८ ॥ (10.30:38)

*evam uktaḥ priyām āha
skandha āruhyatām iti
tataś cāntardadhe Kṛṣṇaḥ
sā vadhūr anvatapyata*

10. अन्तर्हिते भगवति सहसैव व्रजाङ्गनाः ।

अतप्यंस्तमचक्षाणाः करिण्य इव यूथपम् ॥ १ ॥ (10.30:1)

*antarhite bhagavati sahasaiva vrajan ganah
atapyams acaksanah karinya iva yuthapam.*

11. कच्चित्तुलसि कल्याणि गोविन्दचरणप्रिये ।

सह त्वालि कुलैर्बिभ्रद्दृष्टस्तेऽतिप्रियोऽच्युतः ॥ ७ ॥ (10.30:7)

*kaccit talasi kalyāṇi
govinda-carāṇa-priye
saha tvāli-kulair bibhrad
dr̥ṣṭas te 'ti-priyo 'cyutaḥ*

12. पृच्छतेमा लता बाहूनप्याश्लिष्टा वनस्पतेः ।

नूनं तत्करजस्पृष्टा बिभ्रत्युत्पुलकान्यहो ॥ १३ ॥ (10.30:13)

*pr̥cchatemā latā bāhūn
apy āśliṣṭā vanaspate/
nūnaṁ tat-karaja-spr̥ṣṭā
bibhraty utpulkāny aho*

13. जयति तेऽधिकं जन्मना व्रजः

श्रयत इन्दिरा शश्वदत्र हि ।

दयित दृश्यतां दिक्षु तावकास्त्वयि

धृतासवस्त्वां विचिन्वते ॥ १ ॥ (10.31:1)

*jayati te `dhikaṁ janmanā vrajah
śarayata indirā śaśvad atra hi
dayita dr̥śyatām dikṣu tāvakās
tvayi dhṛtāsavas tvām vicinvate*

14. भगवानपि ता रात्रीः शरदोत्फुल्लमल्लिकाः ।

वीक्ष्य रन्तुं मनश्चक्रे योगमायामुपाश्रितः ॥ १ ॥ (10.29:1)

*bhagavān api tārātrīḥ
śārdotphulla-mallikāḥ
vīkṣya rantuṁ /manaś cakre
yoga-māyām upāśritaḥ*

15. तदोडुराजः ककुभः करैर्मुखं

प्राच्या विलिम्पन्नरुणेन शन्तमैः ॥ २ ॥ (10.29:2)

*tadoḍurājah karair mukham
prācyā vilimpann aruṇena śantamaḥ*

16. दृष्ट्वा कुमुद्वन्तमखण्डमण्डलं

रमाननाभंनवकुङ्कुमारुणम्

वनं च तत्कोमलगोभिरञ्जितं

जगौ कलं वामदृशां मनोहरम् ॥ ३ ॥ (10.29:3)

*dr̥ṣṭvā kumudvantam akhaṇḍa-maṇḍalaṁ
ramānanābham nava-kuṅkumāruṇam
vanam ca tat-komala-gobhī rañjitaṁ
jagau kalaṁ vāma-dr̥śāṁ manoharam*

17. कृष्णविक्रीडितं वीक्ष्य मुमुहुः खेचरस्त्रियः ।

कामार्दिताः शशाङ्कश्च सगणो विस्मितोऽभवत् ॥ १९ ॥ (10.33:18)

*Kṛṣṇa- vikrīḍitaṁ vīksya
mumuhuh khe-cara-striyah
kāmarḍitāḥ śaśāṅkaś ca
sa-gaṇo vismito `bhavat*

18. ताभिः समेताभिरुदारचेष्टितः

प्रियेक्षणोत्फुल्लमुखीभिरच्युतः ।

उदारहासद्विजकुन्ददीधति -

व्यरोचतैणाङ्क इवोडुभिर्वृतः ॥ ४३ ॥ (10.29:43)

*tābhiḥ sametābhir udāra-ceṣṭitaḥ
priyekṣaṇotphulla-mukhībhir acyutaḥ
Udāra-hāsa-dvija-kunda-dīdhatir
vyarocataiṅka ivodubhir vṛtaḥ*

19. नीवीस्तनालभननर्मनखाग्रपातैः ।

क्ष्वेल्यावलोकहसितैर्व्रजसुन्दरीणा -

मुत्तम्भयन् रतिपतिं रमयांचकार ॥ ४६ ॥ (10.29:46)

*nīvi-stanālabhana-narma-nakhāgra-pātaiḥ
kṣvelyāvaloka-hasitair vraja-sundarīṇam
uttambhayan rati-patiṁ ramayāṁ cakāra*

20. एवमुक्तः प्रियामाह स्कन्ध आरुह्यतामिति ।

ततश्चान्तर्दधे कृष्णः सा वधूरन्वतप्यत ॥ ३८ ॥ (10.30:3६)

*evam uktaḥ priyām āha
skandha āruhyatām iti
tataś cāntardadhe Kṛṣṇaḥ
sā vadhūr anvatapyata*

21. अन्तर्हिते भगवति सहसैव व्रजाङ्गनाः ।

अतप्यंस्तमचक्षाणाः करिण्य इव यूथपम् ॥ १ ॥ (10.30:1)

*antarhite bhagavati sahasaiva vrajan ganah
atapyams acaksanah karinya iva yuthapam.*

22. कच्चित्तुलसि कल्याणि गोविन्दचरणप्रिये ।

सह त्वालिकुलैर्बिभ्रद्दृष्टस्तेऽतिप्रियोऽच्युतः ॥ ७ ॥ (10.30:7)

*kaccit talasi kalyāṇi
govinda-carāṇa-priye
saha tvāli-kulair bibhrad
dṛṣṭas te 'ti-priyo 'cyutaḥ*

23. पृच्छतेमा लता बाहूनप्याश्लिष्टा वनस्पतेः ।

नूनं तत्करजस्पृष्टा बिभ्रत्युत्पुलकान्यहो ॥ १३ ॥ (10.30:13)

*prcchatemā latā bāhūn
apy āśliṣṭā vanaspate/
nūnaṁ tat-karaja-sprṣṭā
bibhraty utpulkāny aho*

24. जयति तेऽधिकं जन्मना व्रजः

श्रयत इन्दिरा शश्वदत्र हि ।

दयित दृश्यतां दिक्षु तावकास्त्वयि

धृतासवस्त्वां विचिन्वते ॥ १ ॥ (10.31:1)

*jayati te `dhikaṁ janmanā vrajah
śarayata indirā śaśvad atra hi
dayita dṛśyatām dikṣu tāvakās
tvayi dhṛtāsavas tvām vicinvate*

25. चलसि यद्व्रजाच्चारयन् पशून्

नलिनसुन्दरं नाथ ते पदम् ।

शिलतृणाङ्कुरैः सीदतीति नः

कलिलतां मनः कान्त गच्छति ॥ ११ ॥ (10.31:11)

*calasi yad vrajāc cārayan paśūn
nalina-sundaram nātha te padam
śila-trṇāṅkuraiḥ sīdatīti naḥ
kalilatām manaḥ kānta gacchati*

26. तं काचिन्नेत्ररन्ध्रेण हृदिकृत्य निमील्य च ।

पुलकाङ्ग्युपगुह्यास्ते योगीवानन्दसम्प्लुता ॥ ८ ॥ (10.32:१)

*tam kachin netra- randhrena
hardikrtva nimilya ca
pulakangy upaguhyaste
vgivananda- sampluta*

27. शरच्चन्द्रांशुसन्दोहध्वस्तदोषातमः शिवम् ।

कृष्णाया हस्ततरलाचितकोमलवालुकम् ॥ १२ ॥ (10.32:12)

*śarac-candrāmāśu-sandoha-
dhvasta- doṣā-tamaḥ śivam
kṛṣṇāyā hasta-taralā
cita-komala-vālukam*

28. रासोत्सवः सम्प्रवृत्तो गोपीमण्डलमण्डितः ।

योगेश्वरेण कृष्णेन तासां मध्ये द्वयोर्द्वयोः ।

प्रविष्टेन गृहीतानां कण्ठे स्वनिकटं स्त्रियः ॥ ३ ॥ (10.33:3)

*rāsotsavaḥ sampravṛtto
gopī-maṇḍala-maṇḍitaḥ
yogeśvar eṇa kṛṣṇena
tāsām madhye dvayor dvayor
praviṣṭena grhītānām
kaṇṭhe sva-nikaṭam striyaḥ*